

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART IV. POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE SOL

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Potentiometric titration method has been extended to aluminium hydroxide sol which was subjected to progressive dialysis to determine the amount of chlorine released from the counterpart of the double layer.

The amount of the counter-ion released depends on the purity of the sol. With impure sols super-equivalent amount of chlorine is released but as the purity of the sol increases, the released chlorine diminishes and becomes less than the equivalent of the electrolyte added after a particular purity has been reached.

The discrepancy in the results obtained by Rabinowitsch and by Weiser seems to be due to the different degrees of purity of the sols.

In the case of KNO_3 the displacement of the chlorine ions is considerably less than the added electrolyte with all sols irrespective of their purity.

In a previous communication of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 115) it was shown that a super-equivalent amount of chlorine was displaced from a ferric hydroxide sol, the purity of which had not reached a critical value above which an amount of chlorine less than the added electrolyte was released.

In those sols in which super-equivalent amount of chlorine was released, the method followed to estimate the chlorine was such that care was taken to avoid the production of localised coagulation of a portion of the sol. At the same time the sol-electrolyte mixtures were left over for 24 hours to attain equilibrium.

The work has been extended to aluminium hydroxide sol, prepared by the addition of ammonia to pure AlCl_3 and the chlorine displaced from samples of different purity of the same sol estimated.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure was exactly the same as given in Part III of this series of papers (*loc. cit.*). In this case aluminium hydroxide sol was prepared by dissolving about 100 g. of pure aluminium chloride in about four litres of freshly distilled water, and adding dilute ammonia drop by drop till the solution was just short of precipitation. The addition of the drops of ammonia was each time followed by a thorough shaking. The water-electrolyte mixtures were prepared separately, the electrolyte being taken in a regular increasing order such that the last concentration contained just the amount necessary to coagulate the sol within the stipulated time.

The same potentiometer and the reflecting galvanometer, which were used in the previous paper, were used in this paper as well. The experimental procedure was exactly similar to that used by Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 1368) in order to follow carefully the two precautions mentioned by him. The results obtained with samples of different purity* of the same sol of aluminium hydroxide are given in the following tables and shown graphically in Fig. 1, with potassium citrate. Figures with KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 are not given for economy of space, but are similar to that in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Tables I-IV it is clear that in the case of aluminium hydroxide sol also, the quantity of chlorine displaced becomes smaller and smaller as the sol becomes purer and purer even when the displacement of chlorine ions is measured by one and the same method.

* Purity of the sol in the tables signifies the ratio of Al_2O_3 to Cl.

TABLE I
Experiments with sol I

Conc. of the Al_2O_3 sol = 8.02 g./litre. Cl_2 content of the sol = 0.2284 g. ions/litre. Temp. = 25°. Purity = 35.1.

N-KNO ₃ added.	[Cl] × 10 ³ .			[Cl] × 10 ³ .			[Cl] × 10 ³ .					
	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	Total.	dis- placed.	equiv. to [SO ₄] added.	Total.	dis- placed.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	Total.	dis- placed.			
0.0 c.c.	0.0036	63.85	79.02	0	0.0036	63.85	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	63.85	79.02	0.00
2.0	0.0033	64.60	80.04	1.00	0.0049	65.60	1.25	1.25	0.0051	65.09	80.66	1.64
4.0	0.0048	65.86	81.60	2.00	0.0040	67.93	2.50	2.50	0.0043	67.16	83.34	2.70
6.0	0.0044	66.90	83.30	3.00	0.0034	69.35	3.60	3.60	0.0038	68.47	85.06	3.00
8.0	0.0041	67.68	84.38	4.00	0.0029	71.57	4.45	4.45	0.0026	71.75	86.69	4.00
10.0	0.0035	69.28	86.50	5.00	0.0022	72.89	5.31	5.31	0.0024	72.32	90.53	5.00

TABLE II

Conc. of the Al_2O_3 sol = 7.56 g./litre. Cl_2 content of the sol = 0.1078 g. ion/litre. Temp. = 25°. Purity = 70.2.

N-KNO ₃ added.	[Cl] × 10 ³ .			[Cl] × 10 ³ .			[Cl] × 10 ³ .					
	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	Total.	dis- placed.	equiv. to [SO ₄] added.	Total.	dis- placed.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	Total.	dis- placed.			
0.0 c.c.	0.0239	31.31	36.40	0	0.0239	31.31	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	31.31	36.40	0.00
2.0	0.0234	31.94	37.18	1.00	0.0231	32.30	1.22	1.22	0.0232	32.17	37.49	1.00
4.0	0.0228	32.68	38.14	2.00	0.0222	33.45	2.71	2.71	0.0225	33.06	38.62	2.00
6.0	0.0222	33.45	39.11	3.00	0.0215	34.37	3.90	3.90	0.0216	34.04	40.04	3.00
7.0	0.0218	33.97	39.77	3.50	0.0207	35.46	5.19	4.41	0.0208	35.32	41.41	3.75
8.0	0.0211	34.91	40.93	4.00	0.0202	36.16	6.04	5.5	0.0204	35.87	42.11	4.25

TABLE III
Experiments with sol IV

Conc. of the Al_2O_3 sol = 7.18 g./litre. Cl_2 content of the sol = 0.049 g. ions/litre. Purity = 167.5. Temp. = 25°.

N-KNO ₃ added.	[Cl] × 10 ³ .			N/100 K ₂ SO ₄ added.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	dis. placed.	Total.	equiv. to [SO ₄] added.	N/100 K-citrate added.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	Total.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	
	̄ (volt).	eq. × 10 ³ .	̄ (volt).										eq. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	0.0330	21.97	0.00	0.0 c.c.	0	0.00	24.90	0.0	0.0 c.c.	0.0330	21.97	24.90	0.00
2.0	0.0322	22.66	0.85	0.4	100	0.85	25.75	1.03	2.0	0.0322	22.66	25.75	0.74
4.0	0.0317	23.11	1.41	0.8	200	1.41	26.31	1.98	4.0	0.0317	23.11	26.41	1.51
6.0	0.0308	23.92	2.10	1.2	300	2.10	27.76	2.86	6.0	0.0310	23.74	27.99	2.19
7.0	0.0302	24.49	2.99	1.6	350	2.99	28.80	3.90	7.0	0.0302	24.49	27.99	3.09
7.5	0.0295	25.17	3.90	2.0	375	3.90	29.33	4.43	8.0	0.0293	25.37	29.06	4.16

TABLE IV
Experiments with sol VI

Conc. of the Al_2O_3 sol = 6.12 g./litre. Cl_2 content of the sol = 0.0624 g. ions/litre. Purity = 434.3. Temp. = 25°.

N-KNO ₃ added.	[Cl] × 10 ³ .			N/100 K ₂ SO ₄ added.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	dis. placed.	Total.	equiv. to [SO ₄] added.	N/100 K-citrate added.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	Total.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	
	̄ (volt).	eq. × 10 ³ .	̄ (volt).										eq. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	0.0820	3.26	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	3.29	0.0	0.0 c.c.	0.0820	3.26	3.29	0.00
1.0	0.0810	3.39	0.13	0.40	50.0	0.13	3.30	0.01	1.0	0.0803	3.28	3.52	0.23
2.0	0.0805	3.45	0.20	0.80	100.0	0.20	3.35	0.06	2.0	0.0780	3.21	3.85	0.56
3.0	0.0799	3.54	0.29	1.20	150.0	0.29	3.44	0.13	3.0	0.0758	4.15	4.19	0.90
5.0	0.0795	3.59	0.35	1.40	250.0	0.35	3.44	0.25	4.5	0.0740	4.45	4.50	1.21
6.0	0.0788	3.69	0.45	1.60	300.0	0.45	3.55	0.26	5.5	0.0733	4.57	4.62	1.33

In Table V is given the relation between purity and chlorine displaced for the sols of different purity used. The detailed results for sols II, VI, VII are not given to economise space.

Here also it is found that the same sol begins to release less chlorine than the equivalent of the electrolyte added, as soon as its purity reaches a certain fixed point.

It is interesting to compare Table V with Table VI which gives the result obtained by Weiser (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE V				TABLE VI					
Sol No.	Conc. of Al_2O_3 sol (g./litre).	Cl_2 content of the sol (g. ions/litre).	Purity of the sol.	Nature of displacement of chlorine.	Sol No.	Conc. of Al_2O_3 sol (g./litre).	Cl_2 content of the sol (g. ions/litre).	Purity of the sol.	Nature of displacement of chlorine.
I	8.02	0.2284	35.10	Super-equiv.	I	3.01	0.0160	188.1	< Equiv.
II	7.92	0.1512	53.20	"	II	4.12	0.0156	264.1	"
III	7.56	0.1078	70.20	"	III	4.20	0.0164	250.0	"
IV	7.18	0.0420	167.50	< Equiv.	I	5.08	0.0206	246.6	"
V	6.56	0.0240	298.80	"	II	3.53	0.0268	131.5	"
VI	6.12	0.0162	434.30	"					
VII	5.88	0.0093	449.20	"					

It will be clear from Table VI that all the sols used by Weiser had far greater purity than those that give super-equivalent displacement of chlorine recorded in this paper.

and has found that with increase of time and dilution super-equivalent displacement of chlorine ceases. This is only true if the sol is sufficiently pure. Therefore to attribute the super-equivalent release of chlorine ions to a faulty experimental procedure as followed by Rabinowitsch, the original observer of this phenomenon, is not valid.

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